

WORKING WITH THE SOCIAL PROBLEMS OF THE POPULATION IS AN URGENT TASK.

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Abstract: The article describes how social problems in the life of society have been of urgent importance since ancient times. The opinions of scientists on the elimination of existing social problems are shown. The elimination of social problems is shown to ensure socio-economic stability in Uzbekistan.

Key words: world scientific research centers, social problems, principles of fairness, mutual harmony, social and material support.

Countries around the world are taking measures to quickly resolve the legal, economic, spiritual, and other problems of their citizens. World research centers are developing programs for the prevention and elimination of global problems. Social issues are studied by developed Western countries, the USA, England, international organizations (UN, UNESCO, UNICEF, SCO, World Bank). The Gallup Center for the Study of Public Opinion in the USA surveyed 142,000 people in 141 countries regarding compliance with legal procedures. Based on the results, the Republic of Uzbekistan ranked 2nd out of 141 countries.

Problems of social protection of the population have been studied since ancient times - since the emergence of human society. Scientists of antiquity wrote scientific works aimed at studying various aspects of social life. For example, the works of the Greek Plato "The State" and "Laws" are aimed at analyzing various aspects of social life. The main idea of his work on the state is to improve the well-being of members of society. He emphasized that creating decent living conditions for people should include the following qualities: wisdom, courage, patience, and the criterion of justice. Philosophical advice is necessary to improve the life of society. On the contrary, he teaches that evil does not end in society. They also express their opinions on the principles of courage, patience, and justice in this area.

Plato's student Aristotle also wrote works about society and its members. In his work "Politics," he believes that if the ruling elite in society acts in the interests of the people, there will be prosperity in society. If he acts primarily in his own interests, this situation leads to deviation from moderation, he says.

Central Asian thinkers also focused on social relations in society in their teachings. Abdullah ibn Abdurrahman Darimi wrote 9 books on social topics. These books contributed to the improvement of social life in society. Imam Abu Isa Muhammad Termizi wrote more than 400 books on social issues and made a worthy contribution to the development of society with his scientific discoveries on social relations.

The scientific heritage of Abu Nasr Farabi is of particular importance in ensuring the development of society. He spoke about social organization and drew attention to the fact that society is a product of people's understanding through their own thinking. That is, every person is created by nature in such a way that they need many things to live and achieve the

highest level of maturity. A person cannot acquire such things alone. There is a need for a community of people to possess them. Therefore, only through the unity of many people, necessary for life and mutually supporting each other, can a person achieve the perfection that he naturally strives for. The activities of members of such a community are holistic and provide each of them with everything necessary for life and achieving maturity. Therefore, he explains that human personalities multiplied and settled in the inhabited part of the earth, resulting in the emergence of a human community. At the same time, he says that in such a society, people should live in mutual harmony.

In his works, Abu Rayhan Beruni pays attention to the issues of social protection of the population. He showed that noble people in society should have the ability to provide material assistance to socially vulnerable people and the advantages of this quality.

Abu Ali ibn Sina dedicated his work "Hayy ibn Yakzon" to the problems of developing people's taste and wisdom in mutual relations, and his work "Practical Wisdom" to the issues of etiquette and morality of members of society.

The great statesman and commander Amir Temur described the peculiarities of observing social relations, such as the conduct of their activities by the elite of society with compromise, generosity, and patience.

One of the leading European philosophers, the French thinker Auguste Comte, the founder of sociology, explained social development through metaphysical, positive stages of development. According to it, society in its development is compared to the periods of human life: childhood, adolescence, and maturity.

Another French scientist, Victor Cousin, wrote: "Give me a map of a country, its appearance, climate, water, air - all of its physical geography; its natural resources, flora, fauna, and I will dare to tell you what the people of this country are like, what this country has been like in history, based not on chance, but on regularity, not just in one period, but in all times. - he said. Indeed, the ability to manage a country is the first factor in building a happy society.

It was timely that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, having assumed office in 2016, defined constant and direct dialogue with the people, working exclusively for the interests of the people, as a priority task for leaders at all levels. "We make every decision regarding the life of the country in consultation with our people, based on direct dialogue. The idea that "the people should not serve state bodies, but state bodies should serve the people" is becoming the criterion of our activity in this direction. State employees, primarily first-level leaders, are not just sitting in their offices, but are going to the regions and engaging in practical solutions to the most pressing problems that concern the population".

The consistent and systematic implementation of such a just policy has undoubtedly strengthened the trust of the people of Uzbekistan in the country's leadership. The fact that the ideas and initiatives put forward by the head of state, these strategic actions based on strong mutual agreement and consensus, are universally recognized by the world community, is one of the main factors of social development.

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It was timely that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, having assumed office in 2016, defined constant and direct dialogue with the people, working exclusively for the interests of the people, as a priority task for leaders at all levels. "We make every decision regarding the life of the country in consultation with our people, based on direct dialogue. The idea that "the people should not serve state bodies, but state bodies should serve the people" is becoming the criterion of our activity in this direction. State employees, primarily first-level leaders, are not just sitting in their offices, but are going to the regions and engaging in practical solutions to the most pressing problems that concern the population".

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A fair and systematic approach to addressing the social problems of the population has undoubtedly strengthened the trust of the people of Uzbekistan in the country's leadership. The world community recognizes that the ideas and initiatives put forward by the head of state, strategic actions based on strong mutual agreement and understanding, ensure socio-economic stability in the country.

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